

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS BASED ON SOCIAL COOPERATION DURING THE QUALIFICATION PRACTICE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7604803>

“Competence” is correct understand giving as for science occupied theoretical knowledge , practical skill and qualifications diary in his life face coming practical and theoretical issues in solving using , in practice apply is to get Also professional of competencies different classifications there is RV Gurina's to his words According to professional competencies , basic and special from parts consists of

Main competencies - each how modern of the specialist efficient professional activity for necessary was _ common competencies ;

Special competencies Demand to be done are competencies certain professional problems solution to do

The topic relevance see coming out if we The congregation interest and work in the market the work giver now expert by present is done ; modern of technologies development level suitable coming professional to powers have to be it is necessary Professional competencies development approaches and tools see _ coming out things analysis to do this of the problem research stage that showed . In use tools to diversity despite the profession education in institutions professional competencies formation of possibilities enough not being used was determined . Cognitive approach more _ is used and integrated approach in practice does not apply integration and decay processes account received without professional powers development the problem each bilaterally seeing to exit possibility gives _

Scientific and methodical level of research relevance professional competencies development main problem students conscious to the activity attraction who does efficient technologies search that to understand with depend _ We are conscious active activity to students independence , activity , self activities design , independent decisions acceptance to do and they are for responsible to be , own of their actions the results social to norms according to critical evaluation opportunity giving organized process as seeing we go out and professional values . Social and professional values we mean social -professional community by recognized _ and acceptance done behavior of instructions their

unity _ professional of activity goals and to the results personal attitude we understand .

"Quality " category in the context of before school of education methodological and theoretical the basics determine their _ based on before school education in institutions education efficiency Improvement of the process model work came out (Fig. 3).

Educational things successful done increase until the end education in institutions pedagogical the process , har one fao liyat type right organize to do depend.

Pedagogical system

- 1) known pedagogical concept, theory and approach _ _ the authors by pedagogical to practice current in reaching consistency;
- 2) student of the person formation effect showing pedagogical principle , tool , method and methods sum of .

Pedagogical system - mutual connected, education recipients rn i education education to the goal referrer rn ing together set _ Pedagogical system integrity character have be _ of the teacher to the student has an effect embodies . This system mutually effect methods , tools _ _ closely tied up set own into takes _ Pedagogical process pedagogical system within done increases . Pedagogical system one how many structural from parts consists of be _ they are between relationship strong to the character have _ They are : teacher , students , study process goals , results , education content , teaching means , methods , methods and technologies .

Pedagogical in the literature It is said that it is pedagogical processes efficiency provide for different methods and method rn i use _ _ control objective _ _ done increase and control the results analysis to do mistakes own on time correction ; of the supervisor competence development direction is it required? execution necessary _

Motivation pedagogue creative to their productivity directly effect is enough He is professional of activity to the goal oriented , conscious feature determines _ Motivation of the person poten s ial possibilities of the subject pedagogical in action laziness or activity , manifestation to be shape and his creative activity the norm determines _

Motive waking up is _ to the activity and personal and organization goals reach for to communicate encourage is a process .

In pedagogues motive home shooting - ula rn ing _ important self - interest , life _ activity in the process himself done increase for conditions Create means _

The purpose of this stage is to develop integrative thinking of students, ensure high-quality assimilation, professional knowledge in accordance with individual capabilities of students, form an educational (professional) problem, design goals and tasks, perform search activities related to data selection, present development of design and technological skills to achieve, to be able to reflect possible solutions to the problem in a symbolic form, to develop an algorithm of optimal actions to achieve the planned result, to be reflected in educational design and technological activities, in addition, the competence is a feature that allows the graduate, effective implementation of professional opportunities in the changing conditions of modern market production must. It should be remembered that a graduate of a modern university has not only perfectly mastered the program in his field of study, but also has humanities, natural sciences, general professional (general technical) and special knowledge, which he can use employees of the enterprise, who can develop progressive methods of applying modern scientific theories to production, taking into account the trends of scientific and technical development, are required.

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